

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

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Deliverable 4.1: Detailed requirements for the governance framework

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

AIPo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
D 1.1	Deliverable 1.1
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
FR	French
IT	Italian
IV	Infrastrutture Venete
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Waterway
KPIS	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Labs
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

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PL	Polish
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
UniTra	Uniontransporti
VNF	Voies Navigables de France
1/2/3/4/5 PL	First/Second/Third/... Party Logistics

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1. Executive Summary

The objective of this deliverable is to develop the main understanding of the scope of the concept of the living labs. The output of this deliverable serves as an input for D.4.2 in which the generic living lab governance framework will be defined. This deliverable was developed by UA, where inputs were gathered from ENEA, CERTH, FRAUN, SOG, UNEW.

With respect to the main outcome of this deliverable it can be concluded that a general framework was made in the first part of this deliverable, and the input received from the project partners, key actors/stakeholders have been identified for the French, Italian and Polish case. This has been done for the two levels of scope for the Living Labs. It is clear from the received input that there is a significant difference between the three cases. While the Italian and French cases have a rather clear view on their stakeholders, the Polish case has not. Based on the received inputs, the interdependencies between the key stakeholders and actors were also determined. This stakeholder mapping has shown which actors/stakeholders play an important role in the pilot ecosystems. These key stakeholders are the ones that will be included in the Living Labs setup. The French input focused only on the inland waterway transport infrastructure manager and its relationships. There is a relationship with many actors/stakeholders, except for the road infrastructure manager, the rail freight operator companies and the 3PL, 4PL and 5PL logistics service providers. The mapping showed that the IWT manager in France plays a pivotal role in the management of the cargo flows on the inland waterways, making VNF, the French IWT manager an important stakeholder in the French Living Lab and in the governance framework. The Polish case provided a more general overview of the stakeholder relationships. Here, the barge operator and the 3PL logistics service provider play an important role. Lastly, the Italian case provided very detailed information about the regulatory framework for the Padano-Veneto inland waterway. In combination with relationships from a general framework regarding maritime relationships, the key stakeholder and actor mapping was conducted. This led to a very complex network with several stakeholders and actors that need to be considered when developing the Living Labs and governance framework. However, it is important to note that the results will be updated over time. The stakeholder identification and mapping will change over time and the generated frameworks and network mapping will be updated as the project progresses.

Overall, Deliverable 4.1 has created a common understanding of the governance framework for the three pilots. Afterwards, the actors/stakeholders involved in the transport value chain and the river management have been identified as mentioned above, together with the main relationships and interdependencies between those actors/stakeholders. During the process, some challenges have occurred such as the partly defined Polish pilot case (meaning that the presented data is provisional and will be updated over time). The challenges need to be taken into account when going over D 4.1.

1.1. Introduction

The key objectives of the CRISTAL project is to increase the share of freight transport on inland water transport (IWT) by a minimum of 20% and to demonstrate on its three pilot sites (Italy, Poland and France) strategies to improve reliability by 80%. Next to that, the CRISTAL project will assure IWT capacity at 50% even during extreme weather events. Towards that CRISTAL will co-create, test and implement integrated, cooperative and innovative solutions in its three pilot partners' areas identified in Italy, France and Poland.

In the CRISTAL project WP4 has a role to develop a living lab governance framework for the different IWT transport chain actors. For the 3 pilot areas also a governance model and implementation plan needs to be developed. This first deliverable (D.4.1) has the following main objectives:

1. Creation of a common understanding of the governance framework for the 3 pilot areas.

From Figure 1 can be seen that there are different abstraction levels in the project. It starts from the infrastructure. On the infrastructure different technologies are added which are developed as part of WP2. These technologies are instrumental to achieve the goals of the project to ensure an increase in the reliability of IWT operations during extreme weather events and an increase in IWT share. The data that is collected from the technologies are used in digital twins (WP5) to monitor in real time or to forecast in the short and long-term future Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (e.g. water levels, maintenance condition of infrastructure components, level, quality, affordability of usage of the waterways, etc.) relevant for informing and supporting different decision making processes. These monitored and forecasted KPIs, along with the raw data measured by CRISTAL technologies and the infrastructure data, are linked to the corridor management system (SCMS). This SCMS system will use the data and the forecasts to develop insights to the users of the transport network. This transport chain point of view, is also the scope of the WP4 work. This means that all the actors that are linked to the entire transport chain should be considered by WP4.

The LL and governance framework approach will have two different levels:

1. a detailed (technological) level and
2. a transport chain (conceptual) level.

Figure 2: Different levels of scope of the LL in WP4

For the **detailed technological level** there are the technical WPs which are linked to 3 pilot areas where the specific pilot technologies are tested (French (FR), Italian (IT) and Polish (PL)). These pilots are managed by WP6 which acts as an umbrella and links the pilots with the technical WPs. The corridor management will be developed as a generic application in WP3, but for the three pilots the SCMS will only be linked to the technologies that are implemented in the specific pilots (colored lines in Figure 1). The outcome of this level of the LLs is a structure between relevant actors which can be used to test the functionalities of the installed WP2 technologies.

Next to the implementation of the different (WP2) technologies the LLs will also consider a **conceptual/functional version of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System**, including all functionalities (all technologies developed in all pilots, along with the synchronodal functionality). The Synchronodal corridor management system, the IWT management system, is linked to other modes of transport so that transport users (shippers) can make better use of the whole transport network. For this SCMS the **functionality will be tested** with small data samples or dummy data. The full SCMS is tested, in each pilot area¹, what the requirements are for such a SCMS, and it is also identified which

¹ Per pilot it will be determined which of the available features of the SCMS will be tested based on the interest of some partners in the project and the availability of data from external entities (i.e. non-CRISTAL partner)

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actors could provide which data that is needed to setup such a full SCMS with synchromodal functionalities. The outcome of this part of the LL is a structure of all relevant actors which are working together on the idea of concept of SCMS. Also, this structure should enable the actors to prepare them on how they could use the SCMS when it might become operational. This will be done by the development of a (possible) roadmap for each pilot area.

WP4 will setup the governance framework and the living labs for these three different pilot cases. So, for each pilot area a different scoping will be developed, which takes into account the specific details and implemented technologies per pilot area. WP3, WP4 and WP6, together with the pilot leaders, interacts with one another to identify data needs and sources for the different pilot areas. The LLs will support in the different phases of the development OF CRISTAL INNAVATIONS to identify and discuss with the stakeholders and other persons involved in LLs any social and technical issues.

2.2. Definition of living labs

Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders. In this context, living labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators among citizens, research organizations, companies and government agencies/levels (ENoLL, 2023).

2.3. Definition of governance

Governance refers to “a changed condition of ordered rule or the new method by which society is governed” (Rhodes, 2007, p.1246). Governance is a broad concept consisting of more than governments. Non-state actors also need to be incorporated in governance, which creates governing with and through different networks (Rhodes, 2007). The existing literature on governance makes a distinction between different kinds of governance. Some of these are discussed below. International governance established institutions such as World Bank, the United Nations, World Trade Organization etc. to settle matters where several states are involved (Klakegg et al., 2008). Public governance is defined by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) as “the formal and informal arrangements that determine how public decisions are made and how public actions are carried out, from the perspective of maintaining a country’s constitutional values in the face of changing problems, actors and environments” (OECD, 2005). Corporate governance is the most common governance field and is defined by O’Sullivan as “a system that shapes who makes investment decisions in corporations, what types of investments they make, and how returns from investments are distributed” (2003, p.24) (Klakegg et al., 2008). IT governance has gained popularity over the past years because of its growing importance. IT governance has been implemented because companies wanted to achieve a fusion between business and IT (De Haes & Van Grembergen, 2004). IT governance is defined as “the process by which decisions are made around IT investments. How decisions are made, who makes decisions, who is held accountable, and how the results of decisions are measured and monitored are all part of IT governance.” (Symons et al., 2005). Governance of transport or transport governance is defined by Zhang and Witlox as “the political and legal structures and mechanisms used for managing and coordinating transport systems, their interrelationships, and the allocation of resources” (2020, p.4). These authors point out the importance of the multi-level governance perspective which means that the governance activities occur at different levels: local, national and supranational level. Often, network governance is linked to transport governance as it is another popular perspective which has been often applied to issues in public and urban transport (Zhang & Witlox, 2020). Jones et al. (1997) define network governance as “coordination characterized by informal social systems rather than by bureaucratic structures within firms and formal contractual relationships between them to coordinate complex products or services in uncertain and competitive environments” (1997, p.911).

2.4. Governance frameworks

A governance framework is “guidance system composed of standard management practices within the governance framework designed to suit the organization” (Talbot & Jakeman, 2011). Such a framework is often used by the senior management and the operational level of a company or organization to obtain a clear understanding of all expectations, risks, performance, objectives, and reporting requirements. This means that governance frameworks shape and set objectives, values, cultures, risks etc. in an organizational environment (Smith & Brooks, 2013). Accordingly, all stakeholders (internal, stakeholders inside the organization and external, stakeholders outside the organization) must be integrated in the framework in order to achieve the best results (Loshin, 2009). Salami et al. (2014) created a figure consisting of all basic components of a holistic corporate governance framework. According to the authors, the framework has to integrate stakeholders’ interests including shareholders and the framework has to integrate ethical behavior among management. Additionally, the framework has to understand how organization activities or operations affect the environment, economics and social aspects. With this holistic approach, the authors want to promote a wider perspective that does not only focus on shareholder wealth maximization, but on the interests of all stakeholders in the organizational environment while encouraging ethical practices and focusing on the people and the environment (Salami et al., 2014).

Governance framework quality

A lot of research points out the importance of the quality of governance frameworks. Shivakumar writes in his research that “a sophisticated quality governance framework is a must for ensuring overall quality [when implementing a software project in an organization]” (2015, p.201). According to the author, five key components are ensuring a qualitative governance framework: the requirements of the management such as structured business rules, proactive project communication and stakeholder management, and communication planning. Next, risk management is a key component containing proactive risk identification, planning, tracking, monitoring, and mitigation among others. Thirdly, quality and cost control are important. Here cost and budget forecasting and resource skillset planning are important. Following, release management by avoiding big-bang release plans and using an agile/iterative methodology is defined as a key component for a quality framework. Lastly, user control was defined because of the importance of early user involvement and the use of the right mix of technologies and frameworks (Shivakumar, 2015).

Governance frameworks for projects

General projects

Governance frameworks are often linked to technical/IT/software projects in an organization in the existing literature (cfr. IT governance). Implementing an IT governance framework in the right way is based on three major elements: structure, process and communication, answering the three following questions: who makes decisions?; how are IT investment decisions made?; and how will the results of these processes and decisions be monitored, measured, and communicated? (Symons et al., 2005). This can in fact also be implemented for other project implementations such as major public projects. Klakegg et al. (2008) investigated governance frameworks and project management for public projects. The research defines a governance framework as “an organized structure established as authoritative within the institution, comprising processes and rules established to ensure projects meet their purpose” (Klakegg et al., 2008). The authors state that governance frameworks have a vital importance to the planning and management of projects. The authors of the paper call this the governance of project management. This are the areas of governance that are specifically related to project activities. Effective governance ensures efficient and sustainable alignment between an organization’s project portfolio and the organizational objectives. Additionally, governance of

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projects should ensure relevant and sustainable alternatives that are chosen and delivered efficiently. Nevertheless, it is important to note that each project has the need for another kind of framework because each framework is adapted to its own specific environment (Klakegg et al., 2008).

Transport projects

The governance of transport has gained more attention in the recent years. Now, a large variety of transport topics has been analyzed from many different perspectives such as modal (inland water, maritime, port) or multimodal (transport corridors), and in relation to policy integration challenges such as transport and land use, or overarching development goals such as climate change. Good transport governance consists of more transparent, equitable and inclusive policies and even has a positive impact on climate change's environmental performance (Zhang & Witlox, 2020).

Living Lab governance

A Living Lab is “a physical or virtual space in which to solve societal challenges, especially for urban areas, by bringing together various stakeholders for collaboration and collective ideation.” (Hossain et al., 2019). The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), the international federation of benchmarked Living Labs in Europe and worldwide, defines a Living Lab as “user-centered, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings.” (ENoLL, 2018).

Living Lab governance is “a stakeholder's partnership, managed by a specific method for a long-term period to achieve some common understandings and objectives” (Ortolani, 2022). It is often stated that Living Labs are a multi-stakeholder participation, which makes the governance of Living Labs more challenging. As mentioned before, stakeholders are often beyond organizational boundaries which makes controlling and managing them impossible. Motivating, influencing and engaging external stakeholders is often the way in which organizations can reach them (Hossain et al., 2019). According to Galway et al. (2022), the most common governance structure is centralized. Decision making power and control are in most researched cases concentrated in a central institution. Living Lab governance processes can even provide opportunities to develop new and effective ways to collaborate and co-create with stakeholders (Galway et al., 2022).

Conclusions

Governance and governance frameworks are of great importance when managing a company, organization or project. Governance happens on many levels and should be implemented with a multi-level perspective including internal and external stakeholders, which is challenging. This includes a holistic approach which focuses on more than just shareholder wealth maximization, meaning focusing on the interests of all internal and external stakeholders in the environment too. Here, it is important to try to define all stakeholders in the environment correctly. Additionally, it is important to have a highly qualitative governance framework. This can be ensured by having five key components in the framework: the requirements of the management, risk management, quality and cost control, release management, and user control. When looking at project management governance, effective and good governance eventually ensure efficiently and sustainable alignment between an organization's project portfolio and the organizational objectives.

When using a Living Lab governance, it is important to know that this is a multi-stakeholder participation which meant that a multi-level perspective is implemented, as mentioned before. Therefore, motivating, influencing and engaging the external stakeholders is very important after defining the right stakeholders.

2.5. Scope of the governance framework

In the CRISTAL project three different pilot cases (Italian, French and Polish) are developed. Each pilot is different so that means that for each pilot a different governance framework needs to be developed. In order to do that, a generic framework will be developed, that will be tailored to the different pilots. In this section, the generic framework is developed, while in section 3 and 4, the pilot-specific data is collected and structured.

In order to define the scope of the generic governance framework use will be made of the work of Schütz et al. (2019). Their quadruple Helix Model of innovation identifies four major actors in the innovation system: science, policy, industry, and society. These different actors are tied together as indicated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The Quadruple Helix Model

Source: Schütz et al (2019)

From this framework, it can be concluded that all of four main actors need to be involved in our generic framework. Because in the CRISTAL case studies, we want to target the transport sector, and the inland waterway sector specifically, we want to split-up the business actor into two parts:

1. A transport function of the case, which includes all relevant transport actors
2. The private companies that are located near the waterway and are using the water of the waterway.

This means that our generic framework is composed out five main elements, which are:

- The transport function (business transport)
- Other (private) Industries linked to the waterway (business other)
- Regulation (government)
- Public interest (society)

- Research institutes (academic research)

Table 1 shows the generic framework, where next to the main actors also the detailed actors are added. In the last columns, the different cases are mentioned. So, with this framework, it is possible to map which actors are present in each case.

Table 1: Generic framework to identify actors in the CRISTAL project

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Italian case	French Case	Polish case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager				
		Rail			
		Road			
		IWT			
	Transport companies				
		Shipping line			
		Trucks			
		Rail freight operators			
		Barge operators			
	Inland ports				
		Terminal operator			
	Deepsea ports				
		Terminal operator			
		Port authority			
		etc.			
	Logistics service providers				
		1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)			
		2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)			
	3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)				
	4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)				
	5PL ('= 4PL + view on network rather than chain)				
Shipper / cargo owner					
	Sender				
	Receiver				
Regulation	Regulators of IWT				
		EU			
		Federal government			
		Local government			
	CCNR (?)				
Public interest	People				
		Citizens living near the waterway			
		environmental group(s)			

		Local interest groups			
		etc.			
		etc.			
Linked industries to IWT	Private companies				
		Farmers associations			
		Power plants			
		Tourism sector			
		etc.			
		etc.			
		etc.			
Researchers	Universities				
		University1			
		University2			
	Knowledge institutes				
		Knowledge institute 1			
	Knowledge institute 2				

As can be seen in

Table 1, the five main actors are subdivided into different actors. So, for the transport function the main identified actors are: infrastructure managers (providers), transport operators (all modes), inland terminals, deepsea terminals (with all relevant actors), logistics service providers and the cargo owners (senders and receivers) (Van der Horst, 2016). For regulation actors, we have regulators at all relevant levels (EU, federal/country and regional). The public interest groups are divided into citizens living near the waterway, environmental groups, and local interest groups. With respect to the linked industries to the IWT sector, farmers near the waterway, powerplants and the tourism sector are identified. For the researchers finally, a subdivision is made between universities and knowledge institutions.

It is clear that there are many actors involved. This means that all actors in the network have interactions and coordination going on between them (Caris et al., 2014). However, the importance of each actor is not equally divided, which is critical when drafting a governance framework. Witte et al. state in their research that “very few local governments have specific spatial development plans for their inland ports” (2019, p.59). The authors promote an Inside-Out approach where inland ports and municipalities can develop their inland ports based on a shared vision. With this approach, it is possible to deal with all elements of an Outside-In approach, but just from the point of view of the inland location. However, it is important to note that there is often a lack of expertise at the local and regional levels, which reflects in the little attention paid to inland ports in governmental policy documentation at these levels. Therefore, private actors such as transport operators and proposed customers often take the lead in setting the agenda for developments (Witte et al., 2019). According to Wiegmans et al. (2015), inland port authorities, municipalities and regions are focusing more on inland ports because of their great importance and their place in the global supply chain. The authors even state that port authorities and terminal operators are the major actors in inland port developments in Europe (Wiegmans et al., 2015).

2.6. Outcome and working principle of the governance framework

As mentioned in section 2.2, the governance framework should have a holistic approach which focuses on more than just shareholder’s wealth maximization, by also focusing on the interests of all internal and external stakeholders. Therefore, the main outcome of the governance framework is to develop a structure in which all relevant stakeholders can be actively involved to implement the CRISTAL innovations to reach the CRISTAL’s project

objectives, which are linked to make the available IWT infrastructure more smart, green, sustainable and climate resilient.

This is done by activities that will be carried out through a CO-CREATION method with stakeholders in different types of meetings. Co-creation literally means „together (co-) make or produce something (new) to exist (creation).” (De Koning et al., 2016, p.267). Galvagno and Dalli define co-creation as „the joint, collaborative, concurrent, peer-like process of producing new value, both materially and symbolically.” (2014, p.644). Suppliers and customers, and in this case organizations and stakeholders, interact with each other for the purpose of the development of new business opportunities. The interaction and collaboration between different actors happen in many directions and should provide benefits beyond the usual products which are sold. When considering the management-related theories, co-creation focusses on collaborative and open processes involving different companies and users (stakeholders) (Galvagno & Dalli, 2014). The co-creation method or process is often seen as an innovation approach consisting out of six steps: identify, analyze, define, design, realize and evaluate (De Koning et al., 2016). The different types of meetings with stakeholders are:

- WORKSHOPS
- WEBINARS
- DIRECT (IN PERSON) CONTACT MEETINGS

In these meetings, the results of the all the technical work packages are capitalized and it is discussed how the developed technologies can best be implemented.

As a final output of the living lab is a ROADMAP to develop a resilient, more competitive, more entrepreneurial regional IWW transport and logistics economy facing the effects of climate change and natural or human caused disruptions. Leitão et al. define a roadmap as “a very useful tool for deploying a manufacturing company strategy into operations, defining and developing effective relationships with business stakeholders.” (2013, p.385). The authors also state that “the roadmap presents a sequence of phases and activities that support the conception of new models, its implementation plan and management.” (Leitão et al., 2013, p.385). Therefore, it is a process which is iterative and happens in several loops. Additionally, a roadmap should be simple, logical and intuitive and mostly exist of four phases: analysis, design, implementation and evaluation (Leitão et al., 2013). When building a roadmap for transport infrastructure and building its resilience, as happens in this case, four components should be taken into consideration: engineering (structural parts of transport infrastructure such as loads and geometry), monitoring part (such as detection, inspection and visualization), risk and management component follows (such as vulnerabilities, future predictions and decision making), and the communication of risk. Here, it is important to use a holistic, resilience-based management in which the entire network is taken into account (Achilopoulou et al., 2020).

This approach is a generic one which can be tailored to the specific needs to the three pilot cases (Italian, French and Polish) by the different pilot leaders together with WP4.

2.7. Conclusions

This chapter discussed the scope and objective of the governance framework for the Living Labs (LLs). Governance and governance frameworks are important to implement in the right way when managing a company, organization or project. In our case, the multi-level perspective of governance (frameworks) including internal and external stakeholders has to be implemented so that the interests of all stakeholders are taken into account. Therefore, it is important to correctly identify all stakeholders in the environment. The Living Lab governance needs a multi-level

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perspective as it is a multi-stakeholder participation. Subsequently, five main elements were identified to define the scope of the generic governance framework: the transport function, other (private) industries linked to the waterway, regulation, public interest and research institutes. The generic framework was created including all involved actors/stakeholders of the European inland waterways. The importance of each actor individually depends on each case itself (the Italian, French and Polish case). Eventually, the governance framework will be able to focus on all stakeholders and actors if a co-creation method will be implemented when trying to reach the CRISTAL objectives. Additionally, a roadmap to develop resilient, more competitive, and more entrepreneurial regional inland waterway transport and logistics economy needs to be created to again involve all stakeholders and the entire network, as has been mentioned many times before.

that the LLs would support in the different phases of the development OF CRISTAL INNAVATIONS to identify and discuss with the stakeholders and other persons involved in LLs any social and technical issues.

3. Identification of the main actors and organisations

This chapter identifies the main actors and organisations of the three different pilots. Developing this overview is essential because these actors need to be included for the pilot governance framework. As indicated in section 2, the work is done in two steps. In the first step, a generic overview is developed for all possible actors that could be present in each case. In the next step, this framework is provided to the different pilot leaders, where they need to determine which actors are present in their respective case. In the next section, the results of the French (3.1), the Polish (3.2) and the Italian case (3.3) are provided. In section 3.4 the main conclusions are provided. However, it is important to note that the identification of the main actors, stakeholders and organisations is a work in progress, as the different pilots are in contact with potential partners and contractors as of right now.

3.1. French case

Here, the input of Voies Navigables de France (VNF) can be found. VNF is the French infrastructure authority and project partner. As stated in D 1.1., VNF oversees the regulation of water levels, the management of infrastructure and they guarantee navigability for commercial shipping cargo ships and for recreational navigation. VNF also ensures the reliability of the infrastructure at a given level of service. As a result, it can be concluded that this partner is an important stakeholder in the French pilot case (Fiedler et al., 2022). VNF provided the actors/stakeholders regarding the scope of the inland waterway system for the pilot and the actors/stakeholders regarding the scope of the total transport network for the pilot. These stakeholders can be found in the frameworks below.

Table 2: Scope IWT management system for the pilot – French pilot case

	Main actors	Detailed actors	French Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		IWT	VNF
	Transport companies		
		Barge operators	CFT, Coalis, SCA, Transports Lalemant, Transports Blanchet, Cemex, Lafarge-Holcim, Marfrer; VNF is currently discussing with five other freight forwarders/shippers. They represent 70 to 80% of freight IWT in France.
	Tech provider		
		Supplier 1 of technology	UNEW, Euromobilita
	Supplier 2 of technology	CERTH	
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		Federal government	VNF, Cellule ministérielle de veille opérationnelle et d'alerte

Table 3: Scope of the total transport network for the pilot – French pilot case

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	Main actors	Detailed actors	French Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		Rail	SNCF network
		Road	SANEF, SAPN (région Grand Est)
		IWT	VNF
	Transport companies		
		Trucks	Mauffrey, MGE, Transports Vigneron, Transports Foulon
		Rail freight operators	SNCF + others
		Barge operators	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei, ...
	Inland ports		
		Terminal operator	Seine: Haropa Moselle: The company managing the whole is a syndicat mixte pour la gestion des ports lorrains; the public logistics operator is a concessionaire
	Deepsea ports		
		Port authority	Seine: Haropa
	Logistics service providers		
		1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei, ...
		2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	
		3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	
	4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)		
	Shipper / cargo owner		
		Sender	Depends on the needs (in waiting of questionnaire)
		Receiver	Depends on the needs (in waiting of questionnaire)
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	Yes
		Federal government	Ministères chargés de l'économie, du budget, des transports, de l'agriculture, du tourisme, de l'énergie, de l'environnement, de la Transition écologique et de la Cohésion des territoires, agence de l'environnement et de la maîtrise de l'énergie (organisme de financement public)

D4.1 Detailed requirements for the governance framework

		Local government	Communauté Urbaine Le Havre Seine métropole, métropole du Grand Nancy; CCNR, CIM (Commission Internationale de la Moselle), some EPCI
Public interest	People		
		Citizens living near the waterway	Yes
		Environmental group(s)	France nature environment, or more depending on the needs
Linked industries to IWT	Private companies		
		Power plants	Syndicat des énergies renouvelables
		Transport sector	Entreprises fluviales de France, Union des Chargeurs de Lorraine, Organisation des PME du transport routier, Association des utilisateurs de transport de fret, Union des transporteurs publics et ferroviaires, Fédération nationale des transports routiers, Union des Entreprises de Transport et de Logistique de France

3.2. Polish case

As mentioned in D 1.1., the Polish pilot case is different from the other cases, where the policy on the development of inland waterways is shaped by the Polish Minister of Infrastructure department with dedicated Department of Water Management and Inland Navigation within the Ministry of Infrastructure. The execution of the policy, day-to-day infrastructure management and navigation supervision is performed by The State Water Management Company “Wody Polskie” responsible for the maintenance of inland waterways. The Regional Water Management Boards is responsible for the same maintenance, but at a regional level. Here, it is important to note that the state Water Management Company “Wody Polskie” is not a CRISTAL project partner (Fiedler et al., 2022)².

Table 4: Scope IWT management system for the pilot – Polish pilot case

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Polish Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		IWT	PGW “Wody Polskie”
	Transport companies		
		Lashing/cargo securing company	Unknown at the moment, the whole IWW service is the subject of a tender procedure planned for the 2024.
	Handling companies (mobile cranes operator)	Same as above	

² The input received from the University of Gdansk is as of this moment not complete because the actors cannot be indicated by name as the subcontractors, who will create the entire supply chain based on inland waterway transport, is still not chosen (the project foresees tender procedure for contracting service provider for 4 pilots on Polish IWW for the 2024). Therefore, the main stakeholder/actors will be updated over time.

D4.1 Detailed requirements for the governance framework

		Trucking/Last mile delivery providers	Same as above
		Freight Forwarder/3PL	Same as above
		Sea Terminal Operators	Same as above
		Customs broker	Same as above
		Barge operators/skippers	Same as above
	Tech provider		
		Supplier 1 of technology	L-PIT
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		Federal government	Polish Parliament Polish Ministry of Infrastructure, Department of Water Management and Inland Navigation Inland Navigation Office

Table 5: Scope of the total transport network for the pilot – Polish pilot case

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Polish Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		IWT	PGW Wody Polskie
	Transport companies		
		Shipping line	Yes, name unknown as subcontractor is not chosen yet
		Trucks	Yes, name unknown as subcontractor is not chosen yet)
		Barge operators	Yes, name unknown as subcontractor is not chosen yet
	Inland terminal		
		Terminal operators	Yes, mobile cranes operator, as the terminals does not exist on Vistula River
	Deepsea ports		
		Terminal operators	Yes, name unknown as subcontractor is not chosen yet
		Port authority	Yes, name unknown as subcontractor is not chosen yet
	Logistics service providers		

D4.1 Detailed requirements for the governance framework

		3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	Yes, name unknown as subcontractor is not chosen yet
	Shipper / cargo owner		
		Sender/receiver	Yes
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	Yes
Researchers	Universities		
		University 1	University of Gdansk

3.3. Italian case

The input for the Italian case was provided by Uniontransporti (UniTra), the in-house company of Unioncamere and the Chambers of Commerce and CRISTAL project partner (*Uniontransporti – Who we are*, n.d). In Italy, the Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure is responsible for the construction and management of inland waterways, while the Regions are responsible for regulating inland navigation and managing inland waterways in their respective territories. The Regions have an agreement with an infrastructure operator for the exercise of some inland navigation functions. The Regions involved with the Radano-Veneta waterway are Piedmont, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Veneto and Friuli-Venezia Giulia. The first four Regions signed an agreement, the “Interregional agreement for navigation on the river Po”, in order to distribute the competences and the funds (also from the Government) destined for inland navigation among the participants in the agreement. As the Italian pilot focuses on some sections of the Padano-Veneta waterway (i.e. the section Cremona – “force Mincio” (Mincio mouth) and the section Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal), the reference Regions are Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna and Veneto. Each of these three Regions signed an “Agreement” with an inland waterway infrastructure operator for pooling in the exercise of inland navigation functions. In particular, Lombardy and Emilia-Romagna have delegated the Interregional Agency for the Po River (Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po (A.I.Po)), the responsibility of realising and maintaining the necessary infrastructures to ensure the free)flow navigation (groynes) along the Po river from the delta to the city of Piacenza (to which the Cremona – “foce Mincio” section belongs). Furthermore, AOPI manages the functioning of different navigation locks along the Po river and the Lombardy reaches of the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco system. Veneto Region identified Infrastrutture Venete (IV) as the operator of the regional inland navigation network (that includes the Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal) and also, since January 1st 2020, of the regional railway infrastructures. Therefore, IV manages the system of locks and hydraulic supports that compose the Veneto internal navigation network, is responsible for dredging the inland waterways, and has also a mediation/coordination role with several other institutions of the territory that have to be coordinated, e.g. for the management of mobile bridges. Both Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po and Infrastrutture Venete are two project partners.

Table 6: Scope IWT management system for the pilot – Italian pilot case

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Italian Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		IWT	AIPO (realising and maintaining the infrastructures to ensure the free-flow navigation along the Po River from Piacenza to Adriatic Sea) Infrastrutture Venete (realising and maintaining the infrastructures for the navigation along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante, Po di Brondolo and Litornarea Veneta waterway)
	Transport companies		
		Barge operators	Fagioli Spa, Tecno Service Chioggia, Fluviomar Srl, Omniariver, Transmar Venezia, Caronte Shipping, Ship Service Venezia s.r.l.
	Tech provider		
		Supplier 1 of technology	ENEA (Fiber Optic, FO sensors)
		Supplier 2 of technology	CERTH (Acoustic Emission?)
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	Yes – please note that Po River is still not considered a transnational IWW system
		Country government	Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti: Inland navigation management
		Local government (Regional)	Lombardy Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Veneto Region, Piedmont Region: responsible for the development of the inland waterway in their respective territory (Interregional agreement on inland navigation to coordinate the actions)
		Basin Authorities	Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale del Fiume Po: flood protection and water resources management (refers to the Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica)

Notes:

- 1) Po river is part of the Padano-Veneto IWW
- 2) The pilot considers some sections of the Po River
 - a. Cremona - “foce Mincio” (Mincio mouth)
 - b. Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal

Table 7: Scope of the total transport network for the pilot – Italian pilot case

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Italian Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		Rail	RFI, sistemi territoriali
		Road	Core Network highways close to the IWW: Autostrada del Brennero Spa (A22 Brennero-Modena), Autostrade per l'Italia Spa (A1 Milano-Bologna, A13 Bologna-Padova) Comprehensive Network highways close to the IWW: Autovia padana Spa (A21 Brescia-Piacenza) Anas; Provinces/municipalities for local roads; Veneto strade spa.
		IWT	AIPO (realising and maintaining the infrastructures to ensure the free-flow navigation along the Po River from Piacenza to Adriatic Sea) Infrastrutture Venete (realising and maintaining the infrastructures for the navigation along the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco-Po di Levante, Po di Brondolo and Litornarea Veneta waterway)
	Transport companies		Camere di commercio, Unioncamere and Unitransporti
		Shipping line	Not regular tourist line services: Altobordo Srl (Motonave Stradivari), River Cruises SRL (Cremona Crociere)
		Trucks	Some of the logistics services providers own their own trucks; local trucks owners. (See Logistics service providers)
		Rail freight operators	Mercitalia (RFI Group), HUPAC, Sograf (Porto di Cremona), FS logistica (Porto di Mantova)
		Barge operators	Fagioli Spa, Tecno Service Chioggia, Fluviomar Srl, Omniariver, Transmar Venezia, Caronte Shipping, Ship Service Venezia s.r.l.
	Rail-road terminal		Interporto Quadrante Europa (Verona), Interporto di Bologna spa, Interporto Padova Spa Several terminals in Milano Area.
		Terminal operators	
	IWW Ports		Port of Cremona, Port of Mantova Valdarò, Port of Rovigo
		Terminal operators	Portuali Valdarò S.r.l. (Mantova Valdarò Port - also barge operator)
		Port authority	Province of Cremona (Cremona Port), Provincia di Mantova (Mantova Valdarò Port), Ispettorato di Porto (Rovigo Port)
	Deepsea ports		Marghera Port (Venice) and Ravenna port
	Terminal operators	Several operators in Marghera Port and Ravenna port	

D4.1 Detailed requirements for the governance framework

		Porth authority	ADSP Mare Adriatico Settentrionale (Venezia Port) ADSP Mare adriatico Centro Settentrionale (Ravenna Port) ASDP Mare Adriatico Orientale (Trieste Port)
	Logistics service providers		
		1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	Paganella Spa, Generation Transport spa, Katoen Natie, Fercam, ASTL Logistica Srl, TCF Rosignoli Logistics, Borsari & C Srl, Fagioli Spa (oversize loads), River Service Srl, Maersk, Servizi, Portuali Valdaro S.r.l. (Mantova Port) Note 1: Some of these operators provide also a barge service. Note 2: it is not simple to allocate the above operators in 1-2-3-4-5 PL classes
		2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	
		3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	
		4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)	
	Shipper / cargo owner		
		Sender/receiver	Consorzio Agrario, Arvedi Spa, Belleli Energy, Marcegaglia, Gruppo Saviola, MOL
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	Yes – Please note that Po River is still not considered a transnational IWW system
		Country government	Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti: Inland navigation management
		Local government (Regional)	Lombardy Region, Emilia-Romagna Region, Veneto Region, Piedmont Region: responsible for the development of the inland waterway in their respective territory (Interregional agreement on inland navigation to coordinate the actions)
		Basin Authorities	Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale del Fiume Po: flood protection and water resources management (refers to the Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica)
Public interest	People		
		Citizens living near the waterway	YES
		Environmental group(s)	WWF, Legambiente, Associazione Persona Ambiente
		Local interest groups	Propeller Club Mantova, UNII
		Civil Protections Organisation	National and Regional Civil Protection Departments and Civil Protection Offices within Municipalities

Linked industries to IWT	Sector organisations representing private companies		Camere di commercio, Unioncamere and Unitransporti
		Farmers	Associations: Confagricoltura, Coldiretti, CIA, Libera associazione agricoltori cremonesi
		Power plants	ENEL
		Tourism sector	<i>Not regular tourist line services:</i> Altobordo Srl (Motonave Stradivari), River Cruises SRL (Cremona Crociere), Motonavi Andes Negrini (mantova) Several other companies operating on Laguna Veneta and other section of the Padano-Veneto IWW (not in the area selected for the pilot)
		Shipyards	C.N.P, Cantiere Navale Visentini, Cantiere Navale Vittoria, CGX Costruzioni Generali XODO Srl
		Others	Rowing Clubs, several other associations for sporting purpose.
Researchers	Universities		
		University 1	Several universities in Lombardy, Veneto and Emilia Romagna occasionally work on specific projects related to the IWW such as UniVersità Ca' Foscari, Università degli studi di Padova, Università di Parma, Università di Mantova, Politecnico di Milano. Several related projects funded by PNRR
		University 2	
	Knowledge institutes		
		Knowledge institute 1	Corila (consortium)

Notes:

- 1) Po river is part of the Padano-Veneto IWW
- 2) The pilot considers some sections of the Po River
 - a. Cremona - "foce Mincio" (Mincio mounth)
 - b. Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal

3.4. Conclusions

This chapter has defined, based on the developed framework, the main actors involved for the two levels of scope for the living labs. This has been done for the French, Polish and Italian case. Based on this information it is also possible to determine which interdependencies are present in each pilot area. These interdependencies can be found in the next chapter.

4. Agreements between the different actors

In this chapter the relations between the different identified actors is provided. This has been done for all the three pilot areas. This mapping has the goal to know which actors play an important role in the pilot eco-systems. These important actors are the ones that need to be included in the setup of the living labs. However, it is important to note that the mapping of the main actors, stakeholders and organisations is a work in progress, as the different pilots are in contact with potential partners and contractors as of right now.

4.1. French case

In this subsection, the actors with a direct contractual relationship in the French pilot case are mapped, based on input received from VNF. Figure 4 represents the mapping. The French input focuses, as of this moment, only on the relationships of the inland waterway transport infrastructure manager with other stakeholders in the pilot case. It can be concluded that the IWT infrastructure manager has contractual relationships with every indicated stakeholder, except for the road infrastructure manager, the rail freight operator companies, and the 3PL, 4PL and 5PL logistics service providers.

Figure 4: Actors with a direct (contractual) relationship – French pilot case

Based on the overview it can be identified that the IWT manager in France plays a pivotal role in managing the cargo flows on the inland waterways. Thus VNF will play a central role in the French living lab and in the governance framework.

4.2. Polish case

Figure 5 displays the mapping of the direct contractual relationships in the Polish pilot case. Compared to the French case, the Polish case provided a more general overview of the stakeholder relationships in the case. The 3PL logistics service provider has the most direct contractual relationships, as can be seen in Figure 5. This figure will be updated when new data is received.

Figure 5: Actors with a direct contractual relationship – Polish pilot case

From Figure 5 can be observed that both the barge operator and the 3PL logistics service provider play an important role in this pilot. These actors are thus very relevant when setting up the living lab and the governance framework.

4.3. Italian case

The Italian case provided very detailed information about the regulatory framework for the Padano-Veneto IWW. For the mapping of the direct contractual relationships, the data was then complemented by relationships know from a general framework conducted by Sys et al. (n.d.) based on the work of Meersman et al. (2010). When new input will be received, the mapping will also be updated.

Figure 6: Actors with a direct contractual relationship – Italian pilot case

From Figure 6 can be concluded that there is a large complex network of different actors that are involved in this pilot. This means that a most of these actors need to be considered when developing the living labs and the governance framework.

4.4. Conclusions

In this chapter a first draft of the relationships between the different actors is defined. This first mapping is based on data and insights provided by the different pilot leaders. From the mapping it can be identified that the IWT infrastructure providers play a pivotal role in the different cases. The mapping and the first insights forms a basis for the further development of the living lab setup that needs to be developed in D.4.2.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable has developed the following outputs:

- Creation of a common understanding of the governance framework for the three pilots.
- Identification of the actors involved in the transport – value chains and in the river management.
- Identification of the main dependencies between the different actors.

These objectives are accomplished in this deliverable. However, there were a few challenges:

- It took quite some time before the scope and the main understanding of the three pilots was defined. As a result a two level approach of the living lab has been defined to allow for a setup of a LLs for the foreseen implementation of the different technologies in the different pilots. And to allow for the setup of a LL for the full SCMS.
- Not all pilots are fully defined at the moment when this deliverable was due (i.e. Polish case). This means that some of the presented data is provisional and that an update of the scoping of a case and the living lab is needed might be needed when the work is done for D.4.2.
- The mapping of the actors in the different pilots is done based on the insights and data provided by the pilot leaders. This means that the mapping is not fully completed. This implies that an extra mapping exercise is needed when the work of D.4.2 will start. This is done firstly by collected data from other WPs (WP6) to complete the mapping. If there is still some data missing a new request will be sent out to other actors in the different pilot area.

The mapping of the actors is a task that is done in several WPs in the CRISTAL project. If we have collected all the outputs from the different WPs we could setup a common understanding of the involved actors in the different pilots.

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7. Appendices

Not applicable

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